

D1.3

Needs and requirements for the future digital logistics ecosystems

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
A2A	Authority-to-Authority
B2A	Business-to-Authority
B2B	Business-to-Business
DG-MOVE	Directorate-General Mobility and Transport
EC	European Commission
eCMR	Electronic Convention des Marchandises par Route (French); Carriage of Merchandise by Road
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
eFTI	Electronic Freight Transport Information
ERRU	European Register of Road Transport Undertakings
ETA	Estimated time of arrival
IMI	Internal Market Information System
ODOCAR	Pilot project for exchanging of odometer mileage records between MS
PCS	Port Community System
ProDriveNet	Professional Drivers Qualification Network
RESPER	RESeau PERmis de conduire (French); Driving Licences Network
RSI	Roadside Inspection
SMEs	Small and midsize enterprises
TESTA	Trans European Services for Telematics between Administrations
TOS	Terminal Operating System
TMS	Transportation Management System
XML	Extensible Markup Language
WP	Work Package

Document history

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1. Executive Summary

The Deliverable 1.3 provides the state of the art of the main digital platforms for sharing information in the logistic and transport field and the gaps between stakeholders' needs and requirements identified in Task 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 and the current data exchange scenario to be overcome by the KEYSTONE solution for a full implementation of compliance.

Chapter 2 of the deliverable offers an introduction to the KEYSTONE project, outlining the planned activities in Work Package 1 and detailing the objectives of Task 1.3 and its corresponding Deliverable 1.3.

Chapter 3 presents an analysis of the data exchange platforms used by the three actor clusters in the logistic sector: logistic operators, freight terminals and enforcement authorities. The analysis followed the methodology outlined in chapter 3.1, resulting in the identification of the main data exchange platforms grouped into the three clusters: platforms for enforcement authorities, logistic operators, and freight terminals. Information was gathered for each explored platform including key features, objectives, administrator and manager, types of managed data, reference projects, regulatory references, implementation status, end users, and associated main functionalities.

The deliverable in the chapter 4 provides an overview of the current gaps between stakeholders' needs and requests and of the current data exchange practices.

The gap analysis was developed following the methodology outlined in the section 4.1 of the Deliverable 1.3, starting from the needs and requirements identified in the survey developed and circulated in Task 1.1, and from the focus groups and interviews conducted in Task 1.2, complemented by desk research carried out in this Task 1.3.

The gaps have been identified based on the data exchange practices currently used among various stakeholders in the logistic and transportation sector, both through platforms and in paper-based formats as reported in the survey, focus groups, and interviews.

The complete analysis underlines the existence of different categories of gaps: digital gaps (regarding the gaps related to the technological tools used for data exchange), accessibility gap (linked to issues in accessing data) and legal gaps (concerning existing and non-existing regulations across Member States).

Finally, chapter 5 presents the conclusions drawn from the activities of Task 1.3, strategic for the future project activities.

2. Introduction

The KEYSTONE project aims to support the development of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system. Its primary goal is to enable enforcement authorities to access data for verifying compliance with regulations governing the transportation of goods.

To achieve this objective, an app will be developed specifically for enforcement authorities and operators. This app will facilitate seamless data exchange during inspections and checks. Detailed examination of various use cases will help understand the dynamics involved in the transportation of goods.

The initial phases of the project concern the analysis of the current state of the art and the identification of gaps. These analyses fall under Work Package 1 (WP1) of the KEYSTONE project.

This document outlines Task 1.3 within the KEYSTONE project, which is a key part of the preliminary research (WP1). Task 1.3 focuses on analysing existing digital platforms and identifying discrepancies between the current data exchange scenario and the stakeholders' requirements.

This work will present several types of digital platforms used by the main stakeholders such as authorities, terminals, and operators. The explored platforms show different dynamics in the exchange of information, with various types of actors involved. There are A2A, B2A and B2B relationships which are revealed by the research.

The gap analysis uses the output of previous KEYSTONE tasks (the survey and the interviews) and academic research to identify the state of the art and the needs of stakeholders.

Several gaps are being identified regarding digitalisation, accessibility, and regulation.

2.1 Overview of Work Package 1

Work Package 1, a theoretical work crucial for the objectives of KEYSTONE, led by Coventry University, is focused on the realization of an assessment of the current state of the art and a comprehensive gap analysis between stakeholder's needs and current state.

To achieve this goal, WP1 is divided into four activities like:

- Task 1.1 Stakeholders' definition needs and board implementation: mapping of KEYSTONE stakeholders and identification of the state-of-the-art activities, needs and regulations, barriers and challenges related to the use of digitalized transport ecosystems enabling smart resilient ecosystems of transport operations.
- Task 1.2 Identification of state-of-the-art: study of the state-of-the-art and capture requirements for the KEYSTONE solutions, through interviews and focus groups.
- Task 1.3 Study of existing digital platforms and gap analysis: in- depth analysis of at least 10 digital platforms used by authorities and other stakeholders and gap analysis comparing the current scenario in term of exchange of data and needs of stakeholders.
- Task 1.4 Digital Ecosystem private and public perspectives: generation of use-cases derived from the transport ecosystems in the particular use contexts.

The aim of WP1 is to focus more on research than in practical work, for those reasons the idea is to lay the groundwork for subsequent phases to improve the quality of KEYSTONE's final output making the instrument more suitable to stakeholders' real needs and for future regulations.

2.2 Objectives of the Deliverable

The objective of the deliverable is to conduct an in-depth analysis of existing digital platforms in logistic field and a gap analysis between the real needs of stakeholders in terms of information exchange and the actual procedures that stakeholders are following during inspections or when they must communicate with other stakeholders.

The analysis of platforms aims to provide a broad overview of information exchange in inland goods transport. To make it possible, platforms have been examined in various contexts, including:

- The European Union context;
- The National authorities' controls;
- The exchange of information between private actors from the point of view of logistic operators;
- The exchange of information between private actors from the point of view of freight terminals.

Each platform has been analysed via web research, interviews with operators, information shared by corporates and webinars.

Key aspects under study include:

- The description of the platform: what the platform does in a nutshell.
- The administrators of the platforms: the owner or the developer of the platform.
- The main features / objectives: a wider description of how the platform works, which are the operations that users can do with that tool.
- Type of data managed: which kind of data are exchanged in the platforms between actors.
- Reference project: project that influenced platforms and regulations.
- State of implementation: whether the platform is in operation or under development.
- Start-up date: when the platform was/will be released.
- Regulatory context: laws and/or regulations the platform are comply with.
- End users: logistic actors the platform is developed for
- Functionalities: main features and operations of the platforms.

The second part of the deliverable includes the gap analysis which is developed to assist next phases of KEYSTONE in tailoring outputs more closely to the real needs of logistic stakeholders.

To delineate the needs of operators and authorities, the research has been carried out by analysing the results of the survey (KEYSTONE, 2023), interviews and focus groups (T1.2), as well as academic literature such as papers, articles and authorities reports.

The survey revealed various data requirements, that vary according to the stakeholder type:

- Freight terminals require custom data, estimated time of arrival (ETA), estimated time for loading and unloading, delays, cargo volume, types of transported goods, shipments and all the data relevant for organizing checks involving various types of authorities,
- Logistic operators require data on road traffic, accidents on the road, closed roads, planned road closures, waiting times at border crossing, delays of train and ships, notification of bad weather conditions on the road, occupation of a parking area, height limits, drivers, and vehicles.

Furthermore, the survey highlighted needs related to digital platforms. Respondents have shared the tools they use for data exchange and suggested how to improve and facilitate the transport digitalization. Respondents expressed a desire for real-time, Europe-wide transport data to enable instant checks. Insights from focus groups and interviews addressed future regulations like eFTI and eCMR, with many respondents advocating for a unified protocol for eCMR implementation. Challenges in information exchange turn around data security, trust in digital transformation, and sector-specific concerns.

The findings regarding the needs and requirements of the stakeholders, resulting from the academic research, are closely linked to the following themes: security, stakeholders' engagement, interoperability, common requirements.

The research on needs has underlined three cluster of gaps: digitalization gaps, accessibility gaps and regulatory gaps.

3. Study of digital platforms

The chapter provides an analysis of the platforms used by various actors for data exchange within the logistic and transportation sector among the various stakeholders of KEYSTONE.

The analysis was conducted following the steps outlined in the methodology presented in the chapter 3.1, leading to the identification of the main data exchange platforms categorized into three clusters: platforms addressed to enforcement authorities, to logistic operators, to freight terminals.

For each platform, the information regarding key features and objectives, platform administrator and manager, types of managed data, reference project, eventual regulatory references, state of implementation, end users, and associated main functionalities were collected.

3.1 Methodology

In the Deliverable 1.3, following the identification of European and private platforms stemming from the KEYSTONE survey, the analysis of digital platforms was conducted adopting the following methodology, composed by 4 phases.

Table 1 Study of digital platforms: methodology

3.2 The explored platforms

The analysis was carried out to identify several types of platforms to involve the main tools used by all the actors of the transport and logistic environment.

Terminals, public enforcements and logistic operators have their own platforms. These platforms are different, and the managed data varies according to the specific platform type.

In this deliverable the main European platforms for the exchange of information among enforcements authorities are analyzed:

- ERRU: a specialized platform designed to enable the exchange of information between national registers concerning the validity of community licenses and the infringements committed by transport companies in foreign territories (European Commission, 2024),
- RESPER: an interconnected database of European driving license archives (European Commission, 2024),
- IMI: a system used by European national authorities to communicate data, including companies posting workers, between each other (European Commission, 2024),
- TACHOnet: a telematic network to facilitate communications about tachograph cards (European Commission, 2024),

- Movehub: a pivotal platform facilitating interconnection among various authorities, enabling the sharing of information sourced from the registers of new member states (DG MOVE, 2024),
- Euris: a platform that provides information on transport operations in inland navigation (Euris, 2024),
- eFTI: a regulation which is aim is to make faster road transport through digitalization (eFTI4EU, 2024),
- EUCARIS: an application that facilitates the exchange of mobility related information among Member States using a peer-to-peer exchange model (EUCARIS, 2024).

Other public platform explored are:

- Port community system: tool used by port authorities to expedite port operations through the digitization of administrative and control processes (Circle, 2021).
- Drive Belt: Italian governance support tool aimed at collecting, homogenizing, and valorising Italian logistics and transport data coming from public administration systems and from the actors of the digital logistics chain (Almaviva, 2024).

Regarding private platforms, instruments used by terminal operators are:

- TOS (Terminal operating system) used to manage and optimize the operations of a terminal (Almaviva, 2024) (Circle, 2021) (DBA Group, 2023).

Regarding private platforms, tools used by transport operators are:

- TMS (Transport management system): an end-to-end software used by transport companies to manage logistics and streamline shipments (Zucchetti, 2024),
- Moova EasyRailFreight: a platform accessible to logistic operators that provides various services related to the offer of transports on the market and tracking of goods (Almaviva, 2024).

The following Figure 1 illustrates the platforms explored in this deliverable, categorized by user clusters. Subsequently, detailed profiles of each platform are provided and summarised in tables.

Figure 1 - The explored platforms

3.2.1 Platforms addressed to enforcement authorities

Table 2 - MOVEHUB

Information	Description
Description	<p>MOVEHUB is the ERRU / RESPER / TACHOnet / RSI / ODOCAR / ProDriveNet central hub that is hosted at the EC and routes messages between MS, managed by DG MOVE (Directorate General for Mobility and Transport) to cover the applications that they managed.</p> <p>MOVEHUB provides the mechanism to exchange messages between Member states of the ERRU, RESPER, ODOCAR, ProDriveNet RSI and TACHOnet networks.</p> <p>MOVEHUB is a routing mechanism that provides the interconnection of various registers (ERRU, TACHONET, RESPER) in competent authorities in the Member States (DG MOVE, 2024).</p>
Administrator	DG MOVE (Directorate General for Mobility and Transport)
Main features / objectives	<p>MOVEHUB interfaces with Member States using different endpoint technologies. Through the interconnection with MOVEHUB, access is gained to the data and information of ERRU, RESPER, ODOCAR, ProDriveNet RSI and TACHOnet.</p> <p>MOVEHUB applications exchange XML messages on TESTA, the EU's secure private network interconnecting all EU Institutions, EU agencies, Member States' administrations and EEA countries</p>
Type of data managed	<p>Data concerning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> tachograph Cards (TACHOnet) infringements committed by transport undertakings and evaluation system (ERRU) driving licenses (RESPER) information about professional drivers' qualification between MS (ProDriveNet) information about roadside inspections done in a MS different than the MS of registration of the vehicle (RSI) odometer mileage (ODOCAR)
Reference project	MOVEHUB project
State of implementation	In operation
End users	EU Member States connected to the ERRU, RESPER, RSI, ODOCAR, TACHONET and ProDriveNet networks
Functionalities	<p>It runs on XML: Asynchronous (HTTP) and synchronous messages (SOAP), other as needed.</p> <p>Message Style: Single cast and broadcast.</p> <p>Surround technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web app: the application offers various functionality modules: user management, maintenance, certificate probe, country availability, reports, configuration, contact management, transliteration and search keys, documentation. Automated build & deploy: the applications were originally building outsourcing, now they are responsible in house for the last versions. Load tests & performance counters. Mock service (response simulator)

Table 3 - ERRU

Information	Description
Description	<p>The European Registers of Road Transport Undertakings (ERRU) is a digital platform enabling Member States to mutually information from their respective databases on road transport companies thanks to the interconnection of the national electronic registers on road transport undertakings of the different Member States.</p> <p>First implemented in 2013, ERRU has undergone continuous development. The current collects data on the good repute of transport managers, on the validity of community licences and on infringements committed by transport companies in foreign territory. A new iteration of the platform is scheduled for 2023, aiming to incorporate additional information relating the risk rating of the transport undertakings and additional data facilitating the detection of letterbox companies, i.e., entities registered in a country but with little no real presence or activities in that country, often used to exploit financial or tax advantages (European Commission, 2024).</p>
Administrator	European Commission – DG VII – Transport; National authority
Main features / objectives	<p>ERRU is a “points” system aimed at assessing the reliability of road transport companies, and consequently their legitimacy to maintain the authorization to transport on behalf of third parties.</p> <p>The scores are assigned on the basis of the type of infringement committed to the company (different degrees of severity have been defined).</p> <p>The main objectives of the system based on the attribution of points to road transport undertakings are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • record companies operating within the Community. • exchange information about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ transport managers. ○ the most serious infringements committed by haulers in any Member State ○ other infringements committed by hauler in any Member State • check how companies operate in implementation and compliance with Community regulations on the transport side
Type of data managed	Good repute of transport managers, infringements, community licence
Reference project	Since 2013, the Data Processing Centre (EDC), of the Directorate-General for Motorisation, has launched three projects, including the ERRU, in application of Community directives, for the interconnection of the national vehicle archive and the national register of authorized drivers, with the databases of the Member States.
Regulatory context	The Implementation of the national electronic registers and their interconnection are required in Art. 16 of the Regulation 1071/2009 on road transport undertakings, with special regard to the provisions set out in paragraph 1 “... each Member State shall keep a national electronic register of road transport undertakings which have been authorised by a competent authority designated by it to engage in the occupation of road transport operator. The data contained in that register shall be processed under the supervision of a public authority designated for that purpose. The relevant data contained in the national electronic register shall be accessible to all the competent authorities of the Member State in question.”
Start-up date	2013
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Member States’ authorities
Functionalities	<p>The ERRU system offers the following key functionalities, as outlined in Annex II of Regulation 2016/480:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check Good Repute (CGR): this feature enables the requesting Member State to assess the fitness of a transport manager, thereby determining their authorization to manage a transport undertaking. • Infringement Notification (INF): this functionality notifies the Member State of establishment when a transport undertaking commits a serious infringement, as stipulated in Article 6(2)(b) of Regulation 1071/2009. • Check Community Licence (CCL): this feature allows for verifying whether a transport undertaking operates with a valid Community license.

Table 4 - RESPER

Information	Description
Description	<p><i>Réseau permis de conduire</i> (driving licences network) is an interconnected database of European driving licence archives aiming to guarantee effective freedom of movement for licence holders issued in the Member States, enhancing road safety, reducing the possibility of document fraud, and avoiding the issuance of duplicate licenses.</p> <p>In implementation of Directive 2018/645, Member States, in the development of the electronic platform will have to evaluate the possibility of extending the Resper network in order to allow access to information on completed training activities not documented on the driver's driving licence, with the ultimate goal of allowing real-time access during roadside checks (European Commission, 2024)</p>
Administrator	European Commission – Directorate Energy and Transport
Main features / objectives	<p>Resper is a network used by Member States to facilitate checks and exchange of information on licences issued, exchanged, replaced, and revoked by them.</p> <p>The network provides access to information on the initial qualification and periodic training of drivers of road vehicles authorized to carry goods or passengers.</p> <p>Resper is being created with the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to increase document security by effectively verifying the validity of licences issued by other Member States. • to facilitate free movement of licence holders by recognizing their acquired rights in other Member States. • to facilitate free movement of licence holders by recognizing their acquired rights in other Member States. • to enhance road safety by facilitating voluntary cross-border enforcement of sanctions for traffic violations.
Type of data managed	Driving licenses
Reference project	Since 2013, the Data Processing Centre (EDC), of the Directorate-General for Motorisation, has launched three projects, including the Resper, in application of Community directives, for the interconnection of the national vehicle archive and the national register of authorized drivers, with the databases of the Member States.
Regulatory context	Use of the Resper platform by Member States in implementation of EU Directive 2006/126, Art. 7, Par. 5 and Art. 15; replaced by EU Directive 2018/645
Start-up date	In operation since 2013 (since November 2016 in Italy)
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Member States' authorities
Functionalities	RESPER is built on a Hub and Spoke architectural model. The network consists of the RESPER Central Hub, overseen by the EC, and the Member State systems, functioning as the spokes under the responsibility of their respective Member States. In this framework, each Member State is the owner of the national driving licence register registry, while the EC Hub facilitates the exchange of data among the Member States.

Table 5 - IMI

Information	Description
Description	<p>The system Internal Market Information (IMI) is a software application accessible free of charge by the Public Authorities for exchanging information among public administrations operating within the European economic area.</p> <p>IMI is one of the governance tools of the internal market.</p> <p>The system actually supports 67 procedures in 17 different policy areas and can easily be extended to include additional sections.</p> <p>IMI enables the competent authorities of each Member State (for example for Italy the national labour inspectorate and its offices), to acquire information about companies posting workers to EU countries and about posted workers. This information is essential for conducting inspections related to transnational postings under the competence of the requesting authority (European Commission, 2024).</p>
Administrator	Developed jointly by the Commission and national administrations, IMI has been funded by the IDABC and ISA programmes. In every Member State there is a national IMI coordinator (NIMIC).
Main features / objectives	<p>IMI is a software application designed to facilitate the exchange of information between public administrations, with a particular focus on transnational posting of workers.</p> <p>IMI assists administrations to comply with the obligations of administrative cooperation at cross-border level in the various sectors of intervention of the single market.</p>
Type of data managed	Information about companies that post workers to EU countries, about posted workers, and the related obligations in force in the Member States
Reference project	The IMI system was developed by the European Commission
Regulatory context	Use of the IMI software by Member States in order to promote administrative cooperation between Member States, in accordance with the implementation of the Directive for the recognition of professional qualifications 2005/36, of the Directive on market services internal (2006/123) and, of the directive on the posting of workers (2014/67).
Start-up date	The first use took place in 2008. The IMI regulation entered into force in 2012.
State of implementation	The system is currently in operation and has more than 12,000 registered authorities with over 35,000 registered users
End users	Member States' administrative authorities
Functionalities	<p>The IMI system covers the following administrative cooperation procedures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • requests one-to-one between two competent authorities • notifications and alerts one-to-many for sharing information with other Member States and/or the Commission. • repositories for sharing information relating to a specific policy area in a centralised database. • public interfaces for allowing external actors to communicate with competent authorities registered in IMI

Table 6 - TACHOnet

Information	Description
Description	<p>The Tachonet is a telematics network facilitating the exchange of information concerning the issuing of Tachograph Cards. The tachograph card is the instrument which records driving time, period of work, other periods of availability, breaks of work and daily rest periods, as well as vehicle speed and distance of the journey. The cohesion of data interchanging ensures XML metalanguage, which the European Union considers as a standard for the European public administration. A key element of the new Regulation is to ensure that each driver holds only one tachograph card.</p> <p>This platform was developed by a Belgian company commissioned by the European Commission.</p> <p>The Tachonet messaging system is open not only to Member States but also to third countries that must fulfil identical obligations (European Commission, 2024).</p>
Administrator	European Commission – DG Move, acting as the Tachonet project owner; National Authority
Main features / objectives	<p>The system is aimed at allowing an automated exchange of information relating to driver cards between Member States.</p> <p>Tachonet allows authorities to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Verify that a certain driver applying for a tachograph card is not already in possession of ▪ Inform the administration of another state that a driver card has been issued to a citizen in possession of a driving license issued by that state. ▪ Inform the administration of another state of an event (such as a loss, a theft, a suspension) concerning a tachograph card issued by that state. <p>The controls, carried out thanks to the use of the platform, allow not to issue more than one card to the same person authorized to drive vehicles equipped with a digital tachograph and to limit the fraudulent use of this digital device.</p>
Type of data managed	Information relating to tachograph cards.
Reference project	IDABC (Interoperable Delivery of European eGovernment Services to public Administrations, Businesses and Citizens) project
Regulatory context	The Implementation of the system Tachonet is required in the tachograph legislation (Regulation 165/2014 and 68/2016) for ensuring that the tachographs are properly used to apply the social road transport rules.
State of implementation	This system is in use in EU Member States plus Switzerland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Iceland
End users	CIA (Card Issuing Authority)

Table 7 - EuRIS

Information	Description
Description	The River Information Services is a set of information services designed to bolster traffic and transport operations in inland navigation and to enhance both traffic safety and transport efficiency. The RIS focuses on the exchange of information related to fairway, traffic, transport, waterway charges and port dues among all Inland Waterway Transport stakeholders. The EuRIS platform provide access to all waterway and traffic relevant information (Euris, 2024).
Administrator	VisuRIS
Main features / objectives	The RIS is aimed at enhancing the environmental protection, the safety in inland ports and rivers and the efficiency of inland navigation through the optimization of the use of infrastructures, the exchange of information and the management resources.
Type of data managed	Geographical, hydrometeo and traffic related data on fairways; inland waterway statistical data; vessel data; ETA
Regulatory context	Directive 2005/44/EC on harmonised river information services (RIS) on inland waterways in the Community. Commission implementing regulation (EU) No 909/2013 on the technical specifications for the electronic chart display and information system for inland navigation (Inland ECDIS) referred to in Directive 2005/44/EC
Start-up date	EuRIS is in operation since September 2022
State of implementation	In operation
End users	All users
Functionalities	EuRIS offers access to its services through either a user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI) or machine-readable Open Application Programming Interfaces (API).

Table 8 - EUCARIS

Information	Description
Description	<p>EUCARIS (EUropean CAR and diving license Information System) is a system for facilitating through national authorities, the exchange of data.</p> <p>EUCARIS is a Treaty based cooperation between countries for the exchange of vehicle and driving license information through an application.</p> <p>The EUCARIS application facilitates the exchange of mobility related information among Member States using a peer-to-peer exchange model (i.e. information exchanging authorities communicate directly, without a central component in between). The information exchanged is collected from registrations of the Member States, such as the national vehicle register or national driving license register. The EUCARIS application does not host a database itself (EUCARIS, 2024).</p>
Administrator	EUCARIS
Main features / objectives	<p>The authorities exchange data via EUCARIS thanks to a series of legislation treaty like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eucaris Treaty • EU legislation • Bilateral and Multilateral agreements.
Type of data managed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actual Vehicle Information; • Driving License Information; • Cross-border exchange of vehicle – holder – owner information; • Mileage Information; • Road Transport Undertakings Information; • Tachograph card; • Certificate of professional competence of professional drivers; • Road-side inspections; • Certificate of Conformity (eCoC).
Regulatory context	Data exchange under legal base EUCARIS Treaty, Directive 1999/37/EC, Legal base 2008/615/JHA, Decision 585/2014/EU, 2015/413/EC, 2019/520/EC, multilateral or bilateral treaty, Regulation 2016/403, 2006/126/EC, Regulation 165/2014, 2003/59/EC, Legal base Salzburg Agreement (Treaty), Council Regulation 2018/1541, 2014/45/EU and Implementing Regulation 2017/2205, 1999/37/EC, 2018/858/EU.
Start-up date	EUCARIS originates from the collaboration between vehicle and driving license registration authorities from Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, and the United Kingdom. stemming from the 1990s
State of implementation	In operation
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Enforcement authorities use services like Prüm, AVI, DLInfo, RESPER, ProDriveNet, ERRU, TACHOnet, Salzburg services. -Vehicle registration authorities use AVI, VHRNotification, RSI. -Driving license authorities use DLInfo and RESPER. -Government collection agencies use CBE or VHOH. -Private collection agencies may use VHOH, if the legal base allows access for private parties. (Public) Toll collection agencies use Toll. -Issuing authorities for CPC use ERRU, ProDriveNet. -Issuing tachograph card authorities use TACHOnet. -Eurofisc Liaison Officials use VAT. -112-centres use the eCall service
Functionalities	<p>The core of the system is message exchange of structured data, based on SOAP XML. Webservice technology.</p> <p>For part of the services, the system offers a web client.</p> <p>EUCARIS data exchange is via a peer-to-peer network, i.e. all the members of the network have EUCARIS installed, and the members communicate directly with each other. The communication channel is encrypted end-to-end between the two exchanging platforms.</p>

EUCARIS has developed a broker application that bridges MOVEHUB and EUCARIS. Messages sent from EUCARIS are translated into EU Hub format, and messages sent from EU Hub, are translated into EUCARIS format. This means that Member States using EUCARIS, can sent inquiries to Member States using EU Hub, and vice versa.

Several additional functionalities:

- Information to be exchanged is retrieved from national databases, at the responsible Member State;
- EUCARIS uses National Contact Points, i.e. for a certain message exchange;
- NCPs are responsible to determine what local authorities may use the platform to launch requests;
- NCPs are also responsible for processing incoming requests, i.e. for request arriving at their platforms;
- Since the EUCARIS platform is installed at the Member States (at an organization appointed as National Contact Point) the platform is also maintained by the Member State;
- Logging of traffic is done at the Member State, where each Member State knows about traffic that has passed its own platform (but not about traffic between other platforms). The logging data is owned by, maintained by and purged by the Member States.

Implemented services:

- AVI service (Actual Vehicle Information), Legal base EUCARIS Treaty and Directive 1999/37/EC. Exchange of vehicle information and registration status for re-registration purposes or enforcement purposes. Input license plate number or VIN.
- DLInfo service (Driving License info). Legal base EUCARIS Treaty. Exchange of driving license information for exchange of license or enforcement purposes. Input driving license number or personal data of the DL holder.
- Prüm service. Legal base 2008/615/JHA. Cross-border exchange of vehicle – holder – owner information to investigate (cross-border) crime and fight terrorism.
- eCall service. Decision 585/2014/EU. EUCARIS is used to retrieve vehicle data from abroad if the vehicle that performs the eCall, is on foreign territory
- Mileage service. Legal base EUCARIS Treaty. Exchange of mileage information for re-registration or enforcement purposes. This service can also be used to participate in the EU ODOCAR Pilot.
- CBE (Cross-Border Exchange). 2015/413/EC. Exchange of vehicle holder and owner information, to pursue traffic offences cross-border, i.e. the offence was made in another Member State than the MS of registration. The offences for which the exchange can be used, are specified in the legislation.
- Toll-EETS. 2019/520/EC. Exchange of vehicle holder and owner information, if a failure to pay a road fee was established, in another Member State than the MS of registration.
- VHOH (Vehicle Owner-Holder). Based on a multilateral or bilateral treaty. Exchange of vehicle holder and owner information, to pursue traffic offences cross-border, or settle parking tickets, collect toll, congestion charge, etc., whatever is within the scope of the base treaty.
- ERRU. European Register of Road Transport Undertakings. Commission Regulation 2016/403 (Current version, upcoming new version ERRU 3.0). Member States choose between using EUCARIS or MOVEHub. One network, connected by EUCARIS broker.
- RESPER. Driving License Network. 2006/126/EC. Member States choose between using EUCARIS or MOVEHub. One network, connected by EUCARIS broker.
- TACHOnet. Tachograph card exchange. Commission Regulation 165/2014. Member States choose between using EUCARIS or MOVEHub. One network, connected by EUCARIS broker.
- ProDriveNet. Professional Drivers Network. 2003/59/EC. Exchange on certificate of professional competence, required for professional drivers. Member States choose between using EUCARIS or MOVEHub. One network, connected by EUCARIS broker.
- Salzburg services. Legal base Salzburg Agreement (Treaty). Member States offer each other mutual assistance in follow-up to CBE cases, specifically if the name or address of the liable person cannot be established, or if the fine is not paid.
- VAT services. Council Regulation 2018/1541. Strengthen cooperation in the field of value added tax.
- RSI. 2014/45/EU, Implementing Regulation 2017/2205. Notify results of road-side inspections.
- VHRNotification. 1999/37/EC. Notification of (re-)registration, to the Member State where the vehicle was registered previously.
- PTIRReport. Legal base EUCARIS Treaty. Exchange of PTI results.
- IVI. 2018/858/EU. Exchange of electronic Certificate of Conformity (eCoC) between type approval authorities and/or registration authorities.

Table 9 - eFTI / eFTI platforms / eFTi gates

Information	Description
Description	Electronic freight transport information (eFTI) is a regulation which is aim is to make faster road transport through digitalization. The goal is to provide a standardized set of data useful not only for cargo movement check for the authorities but also for the business-to-business communication (eFTI4EU, 2024) (ITS Finland, 2023).
Administrator	EU / DG move
Main features / objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The goal is to create an EU wide harmonize exchange environment, that will allow business to prove compliance with the number of provisions that apply to the transports of goods in a uniform way from a single source. The legislative process to permit eFTI involved 6 EU legislative pieces and more than 100 national legislations. The legislation obliges authorities to accept information provided electronically by operators through an IT system which will be certified. These certified IT systems will be call eFTI platforms. If these tools are not made by the operators by their own the IT providers which will made the platforms and sell to the market should be certified as a company and not only as a platform in order to prove the three are able to guarantee all the conformity with all the eFTI requirements. The certification for platforms and providers will be authorized by a Conformity assessment body that is accredited by EU. The certification will be obtained through a single uniformed certification process. The certification is one and valid in all European union there is no need to do the certification for every country of EU. The eFTI gates will be the IT platforms for member states that will allow authorities to interface with eFTI platforms (used by operators), every EU country will have his own eFTI gate that will be able to communicate with the others. Reduce environmental impact of transports (1300+ tones CO2 emissions saving from 2020 to 2040, and up to 900.00 trees saved every year). Reduce economic cost for countries, eFTI will bring a reduction of economic costs in terms of administrative cost savings (20-27 billion of euros from 2020 to 2024), work hours (75-102 million of euros per year). The electronic controls will make more efficient the operations for authorities reducing risks of frauds and improving monitoring of transports making better statistics.
Type of data managed	Data related transportation of goods, monitoring of goods, monitoring of operators, CO2 emission.
Start-up date	Regulation was released in august 2020, the start for the applications will be in august 2024, the start of the obligation for the authorities to accept eFTI data will be in August 2026, the end of all the implementation process will be in February 2029. (ITS Finland, 2023)
State of implementation	Under development
End users	EU Authorities, transports operators.
Functionalities	<p>Regulation and platforms will make easier authorities controls regarding goods without no need of a huge number of paper documents anymore thanks to digital instruments that will allow the exchange of information with simples QR codes.</p> <p>Check of good and cargo transported, check of operators who are transporting goods, with this information available not only for authorities but also for the other stakeholders involved in that transport's operations (business to business platform).</p> <p>CO2 emission calculator integrated on the platform, eFTI platforms will use to prove the reduction of emission in multimodal transport as asked in the proposal of combined transport directive.</p>

Table 10 - Drive Belt

Information	Description
Description	Drive Belt is an Italian governance support tool aimed at collecting, homogenizing and valorising Italian logistics and transport data coming from public administration systems and from the actors of the digital logistics chain (Customs Agency, ANAS, FS, ISTAT, AdSP, MISE, Ministry of the Environment, Interports, ASPI) (Almaviva, 2024).
Administrator	Almaviva
Main features / objectives	<p>Drive Belt serves as a tool to support the governance aiming to analyse the vast amount of collected data and provide dynamic interpretations to formulate strategic insights useful for institutional decision-makers.</p> <p>The Drive Belt system includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a "Monitoring System" to provide structured and consistent periodic reporting, built upon the collected information on supply and demand. • a "Strategic Dashboard" to facilitate strategic analyses and scenario planning by analysing Big Data, aiming to support scenario analyses for evaluating initiatives and interventions in logistics and studying the impacts on the national logistics system due to potential disruptions.
Type of data managed	Data related to accessibility, reliability, features and capacity, cost-effectiveness, investment effectiveness, flexibility, profitability, security, volumes, interoperability, modal balance
Start-up date	N.A.
State of implementation	Under development
End users	Italian Authorities
Functionalities	The platform serves as a tool, though the construction of KPIs, use cases and scenarios, in the comparative evaluation process and intervention planning within the logistics domain. Additionally, it serves as an evaluation instrument for solutions, enabling the identification and planning of strategies for the sector.

Table 11 - Extended Port Community System

Information	Description
Description	<p>The Extended Port Community System (Sinfomar, implemented in the port of Trieste as its inaugural project) has been designed to function as a unified platform digitally connecting public and private stakeholders, thereby effectively implementing the operations of the entire port community.</p> <p>Involving a multitude of stakeholders – ranging from the Customs Authority to the Coast Guard, from freight forwarders to transportation and MTO providers, from last-mile logistic operators to sorting companies, from railway companies to internal terminals – the system facilitates the enhancement of efficiency and traffic flow to and from ports. Simultaneously, it serves as a crucial tool for control and monitoring.</p> <p>The Expanded Port Community System developed by Circle is the solution used by the Port Authority of La Spezia and Marina di Carrara, Autorità Portuale del Mar Ligure Orientale (Circle, 2021).</p>
Administrator	Circle Group
Main features / objectives	<p>Benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete digital management of cargo and vehicle handling • Increased efficiency and flow of transportation to/from ports • Acceleration of bureaucratic-administrative procedures • Immediate and real-time validation/certification by competent authorities • Federative and interoperable approach with various ICT system network • Port Rail Platform
Type of data managed	Vehicle, Cargo, Operation, Customs data
Start-up date	Solution in the Port of Trieste since 2014
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Freight terminals like interports, multipurpose terminal, containers ports but also haulers, and supply chain companies.
Functionalities	<p>Currently organized into 13 modules, the suite allows for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital management of inbound and outbound freight and vehicle handling for all carriers (ship/train/truck), ensuring complete process traceability. • Automation of port access applications via a "single window" approach, expediting administrative procedures and paperwork related to port traffic with automatic data entry. • Generation of digital statements for various Port Community stakeholders. • Provision of comparative analysis and both aggregated and non-aggregated statistical data. • Interoperability with ICT platforms developed by different stakeholders, public and private, for supply chain management and optimization.

Table 12 - AIDA

Information	Description
Description	AIDA (Automazione Integrata Dogane Accise), the information system of the Customs and Monopolies Agency, has been operational since November 10, 2003. Thanks to its innovative features, AIDA remains one of the most advanced tools used by customs authorities to facilitate their activities (ADM, 2024).
Administrator	Italian Custom and monopolies agency (Agenzia delle dogane e dei monopoli)
Main features / objectives	AIDA aims to simplify and optimize customs and fiscal operations by harmonizing processes related to import procedures and domicile management.
Type of data managed	<p>AIDA offers functionalities related to themes such as (ADM, I progetti di AIDA, 2024) :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applicative cooperation between the portal and entities: Custom single window, digital payment, Customs Clearance at Sea, Otello (Online Tax Refund at Exit: Light Lane Optimization) • Digitalization of customs processes: Fast corridor, electronic file, custom procedure in the ports, but also European and Italian database regarding monitoring of goods, economic operators and exports, EMCS - Electronic DAA (Administrative Accompanying Document) • Digitalization of excise duties Accounting of energy and alcohol products sector, declaration of electrical energy and natural gas sectors, EMCS - Electronic DAA (Administrative Accompanying Document) • Anti-counterfeiting efforts • AIDA reengineering: Goods presentation, import declarations
Start-up date	November 2003
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Logistic operators, customs authorities, enforcement authorities, Ports authorities.
Functionalities	The information derived from customs processes is made available via the network to relevant or competent entities (both national and community organizations). The computer system has progressively integrated various functional areas and existing subsystems to become the focal point around which the digitalization of interactions with users and administrations takes place. The interoperability portal between administrations and between these and users (Aida Services for Interoperability) makes the integrated processes operational for the administrations involved in the single window, offering new interactive services to users. (ADM, AIDA, 2024)

3.2.2 Platforms addressed to logistic operators

Table 13 - SGA

Information	Description
Description	SGA is an innovative, fully integrated software solution for managing transport, logistic, and shipping phases. SGA is a TMS (Transportation Management System) solution utilized by national and international transportation, logistics, and shipping companies. The system coordinates, through simple operations, the central moments of business operations, ensuring optimization of costs and times (Gruber, 2023) (Zucchetti, 2024).
Administrator	SIMA srl, Zucchetti Group
Main features / objectives	SGA provides customized solutions for efficiently planning and managing transport, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sea shipments, • Road shipments, • Air shipments, • Fleet management, • Supply chain management, • Customs documentation management, • Customer Relationship Management, • Z Track, • Maintenance, • Logistic warehouse, • Accounting, • Analysis, • Document archiving, • Container positioning, • Hires.
Type of data managed	Relating to road shipments: cargo, vehicle, truck driver data
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Transport operators
Functionalities	Functionalities of the Road Shipments module: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normal, simplified, model-based, automatic creation via EDI • Shipments online, with pickup, to warehouse, from correspondent • Shipments to consignee, to correspondent, to warehouse • Taxation from tariff, commercial offers, models • Automatic determinations: returns, traffic lines, • Warehouse deposits/locations, etc. • Review and finalisation of charges (customers/suppliers) • Immediate invoicing of individual practices, • Real-time practice profitability and benchmarking against standard values • Profit sharing • Full process for advances, collections/cash on delivery, MRN, customs bills • Operational management of ADR and exemption scoring • Returnable pallets with reporting to customers and suppliers • Customizable additional checks during practice entry • Receipt/sending of delivery outcomes (manual and automatic) • Analysis of service levels for correspondents and carriers (delivery times)

3.2.3 Platforms addressed to freight terminals

Table 14 - EDIGES

Information	Description
Description	EDIGES, the Electronic Data Interchange (for) Intermodal Global European Standard, is the new standard for data exchange in combined transport. Introduced by Hupac in 2005, the system is currently further developed by the EDIGES consortium. Most terminals in the Hupac network have adopted EDIGES, including CIM S.P.A. Interporto di Novara (Circle, 2021).
Administrator	EDIGES consortium
Main features / objectives	EDIGES represents a set of easily implementable standard messages that facilitate automatic real-time data exchange among different stakeholders within an intermodal transport chain, including transport companies, intermodal operators, railway enterprises and terminals. EDIGES enables communication between the customer's information system and the Hupac system through XML standards, resulting in operational efficiencies. The functionalities offered by Ediges include e-booking, tracking, e-billing. The WOLF customer platform, accessible from any device and browser, ensures all clients, including terminals, to manage all transportation phases and the related necessary data. The WOLF platform allows you to: book shipments, access tracking tools, print the CO2 reduction certificate, and establish who has access to various functions.
Type of data managed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loading unit information, • Notification of the arrival of the truck at departure terminal and destination terminal, • Lead time, • Loading Unit ETP • Terminal information • Commercial timetable, • Public timetable, • Terminal master data (position, contact, opening hours), • Consignment notes information, • Heure limite de remis (HLR), • Heure de mise à disposition (MAD RU), • Terminal slot, • Train ETA • Operational timetable, • Train disruption • Transfer of liability from the RU to the TO
Start-up date	2005
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Terminal operators, Railway Undertakings, Intermodal Operators.
Functionalities	<p>Messages flow in Logistic Service Providers concerns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Messages from Logistic Provider to Intermodal Operator, • Messages from Intermodal Operator to Logistic Service Provider, • Messages from Terminal Operator to Logistic Service Provider. <p>Messages flow in Railway Undertakings concerns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Messages from Intermodal Operator to Railway Undertaking, • Messages from Railway Undertaking to Intermodal Operator, • Messages Railway Undertaking to Terminal Operator.

Table 15 - Circle Milos Tos

Information	Description
Description	<p>Milos TOS suite is developed to guarantee a comprehensive management of terminal activities throughout systems (Circle, 2021). Milos allow logistic, administrative and customs operations to be effectively and jointly managed in a unique platform. Milos is interoperable with Port Community Systems, shippers, National Customs Single Window. The most important benefits are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective control of customs and administrative operations • Full interoperability with Port Community Systems • Integrated digitalisation of Rail, Vessel, Yard and Gate activities • Mobile APPs availability • Optimisation of gate, equipment and HR management • Higher yard & gate productivity and handling efficiency • Time and cost savings
Administrator	Circle Group
Main features / objectives	<p>Milos' suite is composed by several modules which can be useful for different task like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rail operations • Vessel management • E-invoice reports, Invoicing and ERP Integration • Gate operations and information • Yard management • Custom clearance management • IoT
Type of data managed	Vehicle, Cargo, Operation, Transport status forecast and actual data, Customs data
Start-up date	2019
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Freight terminals like multipurpose terminal, containers ports but also haulers, and supply chain companies.
Functionalities	<p>Basic features (Rail management, vessel management, yard management, app Milos Mobile), Added value innovative module (Booking pre-arrival, Equipment integration, Optimiser Planner, Custom registers, Quotation and invoice, Gate automation, Wight management, HR management, Stuffing & Stripping, Productivity tool) Connectors with other actors (Maritime, Rail, Road, PCS, Customs, ERP) Users can use Milos through a website or a mobile app.</p>

Table 16 - Almaviva Moova PCS and TOS

Information	Description
Description	The Digital terminal ecosystem Moova is an innovative Terminal Operating System and Port Community Systems. It is specifically designed to manage mobility of goods in order to facilitate import export operations through a integration between IoT systems and infrastructural assets. (Almaviva, 2024)
Administrator	Almaviva
Main features / objectives	<p>The TOS and PCS solutions manages the handling and services related to goods, including bulk liquid or solid cargo. It encompasses several stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pre-arrival planning: Forecasting goods before their arrival. 2. Goods reception: Handling goods via ship, train, or road. 3. Internal terminal management: Processing and handling goods within the terminal before potential storage or dispatch. 4. End-to-end supply chain management: It covers the entire logistics process. 5. Customs clearance and management: Interfaces with the AIDA system. The exchange with AIDA streamlines customs control procedures at the terminal by comparing actual stock in the yard with the data available in the customs portal. 6. PCS (Port Community System) exchange: Facilitates communication between the maritime and rail worlds. This exchange is particularly useful for bulk cargo, as there is no common IT language. The PCS bridges the gap. 7. Portals for shippers and transport companies: These portals allow booking of goods, simplifying bureaucracy. They are accessible to both shippers and carriers, automating processes. 8. Platform architecture: The platform is organized using a modular and scalable microservices architecture. It is cloud-based but also adaptable to hybrid usage scenarios. The web interface caters to both desktop and mobile users, facilitating field use. 9. Authority interface: The PCS interfaces with customs and, if needed, port authorities.
Type of data managed	<p>The TOS manage several operative data and operations like:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Gate Automation 2) Warehouse Management 3) Yard Management 4) Technical Inspections 5) Vessel Management 6) Field Management 7) Service control room <p>In the management of port community system operation that tool also elaborate several documents and data like:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Import export process 2) State of ports, goods, ships, train and road transport 3) Documents (Ships schedule, delivery order, discharge order, crew list, list of goods, notice of arrival, customs documents...)
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Freight terminals like multipurpose terminal, ports but also haulers, and supply chain companies, enforce and ports authorities.
Functionalities	<p>The TOS and PCS are based on OpenSource technology and on microservices, the suite offer a web interface for the logistic operators with the identification based on SPID, CIE ed eIDAS.</p> <p>A mobile app for ports authorities and road haulage.</p> <p>A customizable interface to offer a tailor- made service for the users.</p> <p>Connectors and API with external services (AIDA, PCS...) but also with infrastructure (cranes, sensors, video surveillance cameras...)</p>

Table 17 - Almviva Moova EasyRailFreight

Information	Description
Description	Moova EasyRailFreight is a comprehensive platform accessible to logistic operators, providing various services related to the offer of transports on the market and tracking of goods (Almviva, 2024).
Administrator	Almviva
Main features / objectives	<p>From a functional perspective, the tool is divided into distinct and self-consistent modules that handle the management of information related to various functional areas:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Service Showcase: A module for consulting the offer of freight transport services of type 'T2T' or 'D2D' 2) Track & Trace: A module for monitoring shipments of goods, both through a geographical map view and a concise tabular view with key transportation information. 3) Service Configuration: A module for entering end-to-end service description information provided by operators, terminal operators, and trucking companies as the foundation of the showcase. 4) A guide for business: Used to verify the feasibility of new transports.
Type of data managed	<p>There are four categories of data and information managed by EasyRailFreight:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Intermodal service (E2E service catalog, Logistic service provider, freight network, data about customer) 2) Intermodal service status (shipment, freight journey, shipment status processing, freight journey status processing, shipment status notification) 3) Environment (GEO coding, Routing, environmental sustainability) 4) Business widget (map viewer, shipment viewer)
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Multimodal logistic operators and actors, terminals, road transport operators, rail companies.
Functionalities	<p>App mobile and web portal to help logistic actors in the operations. The platform also has connectors and API and offer a dashboard which can show useful KPI.</p> <p>The suit offers a track and tracing system. There are three different interfaces to make more suitable the platforms for the different operators.</p>

Table 18 - DBA Group ITOS Suite SEAHORSE

Information	Description
Description	The Suite SEAHORSE coordinates the delivery and collection of goods (VBS tool), manages the operations in the terminal (I-TOS) and makes digital the manoeuvring processes in rail terminals (RSS). The Suite is also connected with EDIGES and offer report and KPI and improve the safety in terminals (DBA Group, 2023).
Administrator	DBA group
Main features / objectives	ITOS is a solution provided by DBA group to manage ports and railways terminals and is specialized in gate management of trucks, the charge and discharge of boat and trains. It also manages documentation in electronic format and offer tracking of ITUs (intermodal transport units). VBS is the solutions for the management of booking at gates in ports and terminals and in booking of charge and discharge of goods from the terminals with different kinds of goods. RSS is a software for the handlings of planning process and operative management of manoeuvring processes in rail terminals (DBA Group, 2023).
Type of data managed	ITOS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Booking (gate booking, delivery codes of ITUs) • Operations about Ships train and gates (train and ships trips, gate in/gate out, cargo manifest, train handlings, charge/discharge of trains) • Yard operations • EDI center • Reporting and KPI VBS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of personal data of operators • Gates booking • Las mile management • Management of trucks arrives • Integration with TOS and gate terminal RSS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of maneuvering requests • Maneuvering plannings • Maneuvering management (composition of trains, check of train damages, check of wagons positions, app for operators) • Edi center (exchange of data with rail companies and rail management) • Reporting: operative reports on xls and pdf formats.
State of implementation	In operation
End users	Multimodal logistic operators and actors, terminals, road transport operators, rail companies.
Functionalities	The Suite SEAHORSE is a software solution developed to a microservices architecture and is flexible and scalable. The services offer app for operators (also mobile apps) in order to make easy the use of the software (DBA Group, 2023).

4. Gap analysis

The gap analysis presented in this chapter builds upon the activities conducted in the previous project tasks (T 1.1, T1.2) and the analysis of data exchange platforms carried out in this task 1.3.

The main gaps to fill through the future digital logistics ecosystem will be identified, starting from investigations into the current regulatory scenario and current data exchange practices among various stakeholders, considering stakeholders' needs and requests. and exploring additional opportunities.

4.1 Methodology

Identifying gaps in transport and logistic data sharing requires a detailed analysis of existing sources and data collection. Gap analysis is an appropriate tool to obtain the information, facts and knowledge needed to determine and identify the gaps between the current scenarios and the scenarios that "could be" or the so-called desired future state (Kim & Ji, 2018; Schatz, 2021). Gap analysis involves several steps that use a variety of methods to ensure as much information as possible. The choice of method depends on the problem to be studied and the objectives to be achieved. The Figure 2 shows the steps and associated methods used to collect data and conduct the gap analysis for the future digital logistics ecosystem.

Figure 2 - The steps of the gap analysis

The first step concerns the data collection that serves as the base for the gap analysis. The survey, which was created and disseminated in task 1.1 of the project (KEYSTONE, 2023), together with the focus groups and interviews developed in task 1.2 are an essential component of this step. Along with the questionnaire, focus groups and interviews, academic research was conducted. The data collection analysis took into consideration information from existing scientific literature, papers, and strategic documents, as well as results from the project related to digital logistics ecosystem.

In the data processing and elaboration step, each information gathered in the previous step is analysed and processed to identify the major stakeholders' needs and requirements and the current data exchange scenarios. By knowing the desired future state, it was possible to identify gaps (next step of gap analysis). This step of the gap analysis was based on the data obtained in the previous data collection step.

Finally, gaps are identified by comparing the current state with the desired future state. These gaps prevent the creation of a seamless, interoperable, and intermodal use of the digital platforms in transport. All gaps and their impact must be minimized by appropriate measures. This step of the analysis was based on the data obtained in the previous data collection step and their comparison with the information obtained from the data processing and elaboration.

4.2 Investigations into the current scenarios

This section is based on the first step of the Gap analysis. As mentioned above, this step consisted of three parts, which are the survey (input from Task 1.1), the focus groups and interviews (input from Task 1.2) and the academic research (developed in Task 1.3).

Input from the survey (Task 1.1)

A survey has been designed and implemented¹ to collect needs and obstacles that currently affect the controls performed by enforcement authorities on road cross-border logistics in terms of data exchanged, digital tools and platforms used. In particular, the survey aims to investigate which kind of data are shared with enforcement authorities and between actors involved in the transport operations (e.g. logistic operators, transport companies, freight terminals, etc...), which tools are used to exchange data and the current integration of national platforms with the European platforms.

The survey was administered to a sample of all stakeholders who are involved in the field of cross-border logistics compliance checks, and it was addressed to the following three target groups:

- Logistic operators: logistic operators, transport companies, freight forwarders, shipping lines
- Freight terminals: freight terminals which manage multimodal transports (road, rail, air, sea transports)
- Enforcement authorities: road police, customs, finance police, ministry, public authorities (e.g., seaport authorities)

The data collection lasted about 6 months (from September 2023 to April 2024) and more than 130 answers were collected from more than 25 different European countries, ensuring good representativeness of the European logistics scenario.

The survey analyses the current situation in terms of data sharing both between logistic actors and enforcement authorities and between different logistic actors.

Data sharing between logistic actors and enforcement authorities

Currently, data sharing between logistic actors and enforcement authorities is a challenging aspect that should be addressed adequately.

60% of freight terminal and 60% logistic operators interviewed share data with at least one authority, mainly with customs, port authorities and finance police.

¹ Deliverable "D1.1. Stakeholders' identification and needs" <https://www.keystone-project.com/deliverables>

Figure 3 - Survey results: Data sharing between logistic actors and enforcement authorities (1/2)

The lack of suitable digital tools is one of the main barriers for data sharing for the remaining 40% of respondents. In many cases data cannot be shared electronically and the documentation to be shared may contain critical information about the company and their clients. Therefore, without legal securities a general sharing of data may be problematic.

Currently, no unique platform (national and/or international) exists for sharing data with authorities. Multiple platforms are used, some of them are developed in-house by the individual company, while others are represented by commercial solutions that can be purchased directly from the market. In some cases, the exchange of data with authorities is done through simple digital solutions such as e-mail and MS Excel. Such a scenario highlights the lack of a technological standard, the proliferation of heterogeneous and often incompatible solutions.

Regarding the kind of data shared with authorities, logistic operators declare that they mainly shared data about:

- Cargo (e.g., types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Vehicle (e.g., technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Driver (e.g., professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times)
- Operation (e.g., type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular)

As regards freight terminals, the most shared data are:

- Cargo (e.g., types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Vehicle (e.g., technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Operation (e.g., type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular)
- Transport status forecast and actual data (e.g. train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep)

- Operator (e.g. authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good reputation, risk score)

Figure 4 - Survey results: Data sharing between logistic actors and enforcement authorities (2/2)

Data sharing between logistic actors

Logistic operators and freight terminals also exchange their data with other logistic actors: 70% of freight terminals and 50% of logistic operators share their data with other logistic operators and freight terminals. Data is shared automatically by digital and integrated platforms in half of the cases for logistic operators, by using platforms owned by the company or open data sharing platforms.

For freight terminals the sharing of data via integrated and digital platforms is more common and the platforms used are the Port Community Systems and other systems related to freight terminals, such as WOLF, GOAL, EDIGES.

Different types of data are shared by logistic operators with other actors. The main are:

- Cargo (e.g., types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Vehicle (e.g., technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Driver (e.g., professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times)
- Operator (e.g. authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good reputation, risk score)
- Operation (e.g., type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular)

The data shared by freight terminals are mainly about:

- Cargo (e.g., types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Transport status forecast and actual data (e.g. train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep)
- Vehicle (e.g., technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Yard situation (e.g. stock, capacity)

20% of logistic operators and 30% of terminals do not actually share data but they are interested in exploring this opportunity. They do not currently share data because they have no evidence of either income or benefits, and they want to keep market advantages. In addition, the lack of an appropriate digital system limits data sharing. Respondents who are not interested in the sharing of data declare that the main reasons are confidentiality and competition factors.

Logistic operators

Freight terminals

Figure 5 - Survey results: Data sharing between logistic actors

Input From the focus groups (Task 1.2)

The task 1.2 focus his effort on the collection of data from logistic stakeholders thought focus groups and interview. The aim of this task is to understand the state of the art and to capture requirements for KEYSTONE solutions. The objective is to have significant insights from logistic environment about awareness of positive impact of digitalization, and how much they are available for the experimentation of new digital processes for the electronic provision of the information they need to perform their control activities. The collection of data would also help the creation of an inventory of existing solutions is created to clearly define the functionalities of the KEYSTONE platform.

To fulfil that objective the T 1.2 analysis has concentrated his effort on discussion about existing platforms and future digital projects that can interest several actors of logistic field like private operators and public enforcement.

The idea of the work was to map existing solutions and identify opinions and information from logistic actors about regulations, challenges and possibles solutions.

In the logistics field, experts and operators have identified a wide range of B-2-B solutions, estimated to be around 400-500 globally. While the market for these solutions remains uncertain, there's a consensus that it will likely be dominated by large corporations like SAP and IBM. Moreover, large organizations, including operators, are expected to influence suppliers and customers to adopt the same versions of digital tools and platforms. For instance, LKW Walter has its own platform, and Project 44, is also gaining prominence among larger operators.

From the commercial platform perspective, the interviews have identified several experiences which included platforms focused on several innovative applications regarding different modalities including e-CMR, blockchain in aiding international supply chains and Internet of things.

From the platforms used by Enforcement Authorities the most cited are part of the EU tools environment like EUCARIS (sharing of information about driving licenses), TRACES (sharing of information about plant and animal product health certification).

Other platforms used to interact with Enforcement Authorities are the DVSA, DEFRA, Port Health Authorities, Border Force, Customs (HMRC).

The future projects, identified by the research, which are considered crucial for logistic are:

- ADMIRAL (managed by Awake.AI in Finland) is a project assessing the use of AI solutions in creating resilient and sustainable supply chains and logistics. Its aim is to develop a 'cutting edge' digital marketplace for multimodal logistics, enabling businesses to manage their entire supply chain including related emissions.
- eFTI4EU aims to establish a harmonised and interoperable eFTI exchange environment Europe-wide.
- Data Spaces are federated platforms that link many 'trusted' cloud-based service providers and users together in a transparent environment, for secure and sovereign data exchange. The International Data Spaces Association (ISDA) and Gaia-X are key examples mentioned by interviewed stakeholders. Data Spaces have sometimes been mentioned as an approach to data sharing that enables businesses to be in control of their data, given fears of business data being utilised by businesses to undermine competitors (see 'Challenges' below).

Input from the academic research

The growing demand for transportation of goods is associated with a large amount of data, which is coupled with the need to share it efficiently and quickly among all stakeholders involved. Fast and reliable data exchange is a key component in the quest for fast, efficient, and reliable freight transportation with the goal of reducing the need for paper documents. Currently, stakeholders face several challenges that prevent and discourage them from using efficient means of data exchange between Logistic operators, Freight terminals and Enforcement authorities. The importance of data exchange despite the individual stakeholders is confirmed by research papers, reports from other projects and other documents available on the Internet.

The collection of accurate, reliable, and timely data is the basis for transportation planning, decision-making and smooth transportation organization. Many of the data is collected in paper form, which increases the time it takes to process the data, increases the cost of bureaucracy, and is overall a very inefficient solution. It is therefore necessary to increase the digitization of freight transport, which will eliminate many of the shortcomings in this sector and will have a positive impact on the entire transport chain and ultimately bring positive synergies on other indicators (increased efficiency and speed, as digitization ensures instant communication between the different stakeholders, etc.) (Wang & Sarkis, 2021). The data held by Logistic operators and Freight terminals, and in some cases by Enforcement authorities, can be divided into two groups (see Figure 6). Each group contains a different structure of information, and each group can be helpful in a different way. While there is an obligation for the individual stakeholders to share data with each other in the Mandatory data group, there is no obligation to share it with each other in the Optional data group.

Figure 6 - Mandatory and optional data

The first group consists of "Mandatory data", i.e. data that Logistic operators and Freight terminals are obliged to share with authorities for various purposes. This data is shared and collected for a variety of purposes; the main objective of this data are shown in the figure below. Their exchange is based on regulations, binding documents, national law (as shown in the figure above), so in many cases there are already shared. However, it is important to note that in most cases this data is shared in paper form (European Environment Agency, 2022).

Figure 7 - Mandatory data purposes

The second group consists of data that is not subject to a sharing obligation. Stakeholders have a huge amount of data that they use mainly for their own purposes. However, this optional data is not shared externally (neither in paper nor in digital form) for various reasons such as the monetary value of data protection, commercial confidentiality concerns, etc. The optional data contain a lot of different information and could be important for the implementation of a more seamless freight transport (Moschovou, Vlahogianni, & Rentziou, 2019). This optional data is collected by different stakeholders who use their own resources to collect and process it. For example, some authorities have roadside sensors that can generate a lot of useful information with the current traffic status (e.g. average speed, traffic count). Likewise, authorities, logistic operators and freight terminals have their own means and tools through which they are able to obtain much information related to operational data. The obtaining of information is mainly ensured by vehicle tracking devices, using Global Positioning System measurements of vehicles. The information obtained using GPS includes information such as individual vehicle movements, location of stops, and energy consumption profiles (Shoman, a iní, 2023). As mentioned above, sharing this data can add value to the entire transportation process. Its potential purposes when shared among stakeholders are shown in the figure below. The identified information is not part of any documents carried on board the means of transport during transport. It is held by the stakeholders in digital form and is real-time data (Læggran, Pitera, T, & Tørset, 2023).

Figure 8 - Optional data purposes (Source: authors based on Læggran, et al., 2023)

Based on the facts found, it can be concluded that most of the data is held by the Freight terminals and Logistic operators, with Enforcements authorities requiring a lot of data from them (depending on the competence of the authority) in order to ensure the safe and legal transport of goods and things. To achieve fully digital data exchange, it is necessary to ensure the synergy and cooperation of all parties involved and to ensure that the needs and requirements of the stakeholders are met when data is exchanged electronically between them.

Currently, many documents are used to transfer goods, personnel, and schedules throughout the whole transport process. Some documents are issued by Enforcement authorities to Logistic operators and Freight terminals (permits, licences, inspection reports, etc.). These documents issued by the authorities are in most cases on board of the transport means during the transport, for instance in the case of controls. On the other hand, some documents are created by operators and terminals (contracts, transport conditions, crew, information on the goods, ...). All these documents (those issued by the authorities and those issued by operators and terminals) contain data that are exchanged between the stakeholders. These documents are used to clarify the compliance of the transport (according to the regulations and laws to which the transport is subject, such as compliance with rest periods, validity of permits for ADR transport, etc.) and to ensure and modify the transport conditions (between operators and terminals - ways of handling goods, places of transshipment of goods, ...).

4.3 Investigations into stakeholders' needs and requests

Data needs (input from the survey)

The survey showed that there is a widespread awareness about the pivotal role played by data and technology in improving and enhancing compliance checks carried out by enforcement authorities. A digital transformation is essential to optimize logistics processes and transport sustainability. In addition to this, the main barriers that should be properly addressed are the complex legislation, the cooperation between member states, the geo-political context (e.g., non-EU borders, Brexit, uncertainty of regulations, different languages), and the type of shipping (dangerous or perishable goods, project cargo).

Most respondents are aware of the importance of data and its exchange for enhancing business opportunities and enhancing internal processes. 71% of freight terminals interviewed declare that some data not currently shared with them may be useful for improving their productivity and efficiency. The types of data needed are customs data, estimated time of arrival (ETA), estimated time for loading and unloading, delays, cargo volume, types of transported goods, shipments and all the data that could help in organizing checks involving different types of authorities.

57% of logistic operators interviewed also need further data for improving productivity and efficiency. They would benefit from data about road traffic and accidents on the road, closed roads and planned road closures, waiting times at border crossing, delays of train and ships, notification of bad weather conditions on the road, occupation of a parking area, height limits, drivers, and the vehicles.

85% of enforcement authorities interviewed declare that there are some data, currently not shared with them, that might be provided by the stakeholders (e.g., logistic operators, terminal/freight operators, authorities of other countries, etc.) and that might improve the checks. Some respondents would like to exchange vehicles information and status such as data about the last RSI (Roadside Inspection) and PTI (Periodical Technical Inspection). This data could help avoid the same truck being checked in RSI several times during the same trip and it could also be a step towards mutual recognition of PTI results. A centralized, European-wide database like the one implemented for Certificate of Conformity (COC) might be also a good solution to implement. Other respondents think that it would be important to have more data to combat and bottom out fraud related offences in a more efficient way. The desired data is anything that could help the officers prove beyond doubt the route a vehicle took up to the point of inspection (traffic data, shipping manifests, tolling data, etc...). For example, GPS vehicle tracking could be used to verify the actual data from tachograph and to exclude manipulations. The sharing of the shipping manifests, which includes information about the people on the incoming ferries could help profiling the incoming operators and target high risk ones. Other data useful for improving checks are about loads, timesheets, mileages or driven kilometres, shipping order forms, weighing-in documents, accurate traffic information and roadblocks, Expected Time Arrival (ETA), origin-destination data, waiting times in terminals, number of subcontracting and transportation price.

The data sharing across European countries is another aspect highlighted by respondents. They would like to have real time sharing of driving license data and operator licensing, as well as data about bad practices in transportation in each country and documents, regulations, control and inspection procedures or protocols specific for each country. Data about drivers and transport company documentation should be exchanged between Member States by the ERRU system, but currently some States (e.g., Portugal) do not use this application for sharing data. The way in which data is shared among Member States should be compliant with regulation EU 2020/1056 (eFTI).

Needs about digital platforms (input from the survey)

As regards the digital platforms used by the enforcement authorities to carry out controls, the most frequently used are the Port Community Systems, IT systems provided by the national ministry, the national customs agency (STD – Sistema Telematico Doganale), the police systems, the card issuing authority and the licensing authority. DBs and software developed internally are also used; some of them are also linked to

databases of EU platforms such as TACHOnet. Some commercial platforms used are TachoScan Control (for checks of drivers' working time) and AETRControl (a professional tachograph evaluator for checking driving and resting times).

According to respondents' opinions, these platforms should be improved and enhanced by integrating new data sources. The respondents' desire is to have Europe wide transport data in real time for instant checks. This means having for example the same data on out-of-state vehicles and drivers as they have for their own and accessible at the roadside, (i.e., tachograph card data, CPC card data, driver licensing data, vehicle roadworthiness data etc..).

70% of the authorities interviewed use the IT systems developed by the EU to facilitate the cooperation for cross-border enforcement (ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI and eFTI platforms). They think that these tools need some improvements, by integrating the different EU platforms and making them accessible by a single interface. The accessibility of the platforms and the data currently provided would also be improved, especially for simplifying roadside checks.

Figure 9 - Needs about digital platforms (survey)

Needs from Focus group and interviews

The main challenges emerged in the focus groups and interviews realized in the Task 1.2 are related to:

- interoperability,
- data security,
- trust in the digital transformation of the transport and logistic sector.

Despite support for digital adoption, only 1% of activity with CMRs occurs electronically due to various e-CMR solutions causing interoperability issues.

Operators hesitate to share data, necessitating better alignment with Enforcement Agencies.

Transitioning from the 'old world' to data sharing poses challenges for companies, especially SMEs. Additionally, tracking 'dangerous goods' remains difficult due to limited digital information.

During the focus groups and interviews conducted, respondents explored a range of possibilities surrounding the opportunities for the KEYSTONE project as part of wider 'requirements' in relation to the digitalization of transportation and logistics.

For some participants, simply offering a mobile phone application was insufficient and would add to challenges in relation to interoperability. Rather than adding another App into the marketplace, a more effective solution was seen in relation to data sharing, and this being completed via a 'federated' approach ('data spaces').

Other participants were more open to the notion of an App, or web-based system, and outlined a variety of potential details in terms of what functions this could encompass or achieve. The App could contain aspects such as:

- Status/Tracking (on document acceptance/responsibilities)
- Interfacing possibilities

- Overview of shipment progress
- Qualifications of Drivers (including the ability to verify these)
- Transport unit (e.g. vehicle type)
- Inspections (e.g. when did they take place)
- Route/Destination

The importance of an international regulatory regime for the transport of dangerous goods and the associated needs emerged.

An important insight emerged from the interviews is that there isn't a real need for a singular digital platform, the operators prefer a variety of independent platforms, another thing that emerged is that in some cases the tools are projected in a customized way but for the majority of business the systems are based on software tools already available.

The notion of an 'Amazon style' system which has no subscription fee for data storage was mentioned by one stakeholder. The creation of a free-to-use 'front-end' would allow an SME to scan their invoice and send it to other stakeholders involved in the shipment chain (e.g. Freight Forwarders etc.). So rather than having yet another system, it will be more effective to build an API which pulls data onto the platform when a new job/shipment is created.

As mentioned, Data Mobility Spaces are seen as a more effective solution by some respondents (e.g. establishing data sharing in a federated manner so it can be monetized and controlled rather than this being done by players such as Google and Facebook). Finally, Stakeholders highlighted the need to listen to the market to delve deeper into topics such as sustainability, CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility), developments in new technologies.

Regarding the legislative framework the emerging view regarding regulation is that significant national differences exist in the acceptance and usage of digitalized documents. These differences create uncertainties for operators and businesses. While the introduction of eFTI (electronic freight transport information) is viewed positively, it is not considered a complete solution. Instead, it is seen as a component of the digitalized future for cross-border transport and logistics. Challenges include understanding how eFTI will interact with the global system for customs data and how it will interpret such data. National regulations (e.g., Germany's requirement for drivers to provide their own devices) add complexity and hinder standardization. Despite this, adoption and usage of eFTI are critical for effectively "future proof" systems for Customs Agencies.

Regarding CMR/e-CMR protocols, there is no singular approach across Europe. The differing pace of adoption creates further uncertainties for operators and businesses.

Additionally, the European Data Strategy aims to create federated "data spaces" and control the monetization or commodification of data. Other relevant initiatives include the Mobility Package and Single Trade Window.

4.4 Investigations into opportunities

As described above, freight transport requires the exchange of a substantial volume of documents and data among relevant stakeholders. Currently, this data exchanged is still performed in paper form in many cases (this is evident from the questionnaire, but also from academic research), which notably impacts the environment and transport quality. The different stakeholders involved in data exchange have varying needs and requirements for electronic data interchange, contingent upon their stakeholder type and the nature of the data exchanged. Failure to meet these needs and requirements results in stakeholders being unwilling

to engage in electronic data exchange. The findings regarding the needs and requirements of the stakeholders, resulting from the academic research, are closely linked to the following themes: security, stakeholders' engagement, interoperability, common requirements.

Figure 10 - Key areas of stakeholder requirements and needs for digital data sharing resulting from the academic research

Security of data sharing

As not all stakeholders are willing to share their data digitally, it is necessary to ensure sufficient data security. Individual stakeholders require that the data to be shared electronically is adequately protected. Therefore, it's crucial to precisely outline the required data from each stakeholder, the intended purposes for its use, and the specific responsibilities of each party. Stakeholders intending to share their data electronically need to comprehend and consent to the data processes. Moreover, if sensitive data related to trade secrets is collected, it must undergo full anonymization. Within a digital platform for data sharing, it is very important to define the plan and purpose for the data, including a clear framework and boundaries for the use of the data. Data security measures are also essential, as any leakage or compromise of data integrity would pose significant challenges for the common platform's utility. Stakeholders should retain full control and ownership of the data they share, enhancing their confidence in utilizing the shared platform.

Involve all relevant stakeholders

The involvement of all relevant stakeholders will help ensure equity among them in providing data for mutual benefit. There is a need to ensure that all Member States accept electronic freight documents/data and that all stakeholders adopt this form of data exchange. If there is one stakeholder in the whole transport process that does not use digital data exchange, the whole process of digitisation of transport loses significance. With more data from more operators, it is possible to achieve better aggregation to limit the identification of data specific operators and to ensure the representativeness of the data collected. In addition, the involvement of "all" stakeholders helps to ensure equity between operators in providing data for a common benefit. For this reason, it would be appropriate to make the acceptance and sharing of data in digital form mandatory.

Interoperability

The academic research has revealed the existence of several platforms used by different stakeholders that do not cooperate with each other. This is mainly due to the absence of mandatory technical specifications or guidelines, which has led to the creation of several non-interoperable data exchange platforms in different Member States and used by different stakeholders. Data exchange platforms used in the transport sector vary from country to country, but also from mode to mode (different platforms are used for rail transport than for road transport). The diversity and non-interoperability of the platforms used for electronic documents and

data exchange causes and increases the reluctance of stakeholders to use these systems. It is therefore very important to create a single platform that can be used by different stakeholders to exchange data (European Commission, 2021). The current diversity in data exchange platforms leads to ambiguity and complicates their utilization. The optimal solution to ensure and achieve paperless transport is the creation of a single platform that serves all stakeholders and in all Member States, thus supporting and facilitating the whole process of electronic data exchange (Ministry of Transport of the Slovak Republic, 2019). This is a key element requiring standardization across all European countries, encouraging a consistent and user-friendly environment for data exchange. On one hand, there is a need to motivate logistic operators and freight terminals to share their data in a certain way; on the other hand, there is a need to motivate enforcement authorities to accept electronic data in the same way in all countries. If the form of digital data exchange differs across Europe, the possibility of creating a paperless transport environment is significantly reduced. The absence of a unique tool for data exchange among stakeholders leads to data inconsistency, characterized by varying data formats and sources.

Common and unified requirements

Unilateral initiatives by Member States to facilitate the introduction of electronic transport documents and the exchange of information will have limited impact if equivalent requirements are not implemented in other Member States whose territories are also affected by transport operations. Even if the majority of EU Member States are willing to adopt legislation to facilitate the use of electronic documents, there would be a high risk that by unilaterally adopting such legislation, each Member State will adopt different requirements for the recognition of electronic documents and, more generally, for the communication of regulatory information as valid and binding. Electronic documents and the communication of regulatory information that meet the requirements for acceptance in one Member State may not be accepted in other Member States, leading to the creation of barriers in this sector. The most effective approach to address this issue and its underlying causes is at the EU level, where a uniform framework for electronic document acceptance and common standards can be established. This will ensure uniform and consistent conditions for the exchange of data and thus promote the interoperability of information systems and solutions used for the electronic exchange of information in freight transport among relevant stakeholders.

Added value of data sharing

Stakeholders want to see the added value of data sharing and how/whether they can contribute. The goal of data collection needs to be directly defined. The benefits of digital data sharing for each stakeholder and the added value for them need to be clearly described and defined. The benefits of data sharing depend on the type of data to be shared through a platform. If mandatory data is shared electronically, it will have a positive impact on administrative costs, on man-hours saved on administration, on CO₂ emissions saved on the environment, on the ability to ensure direct and immediate communication between stakeholders. Optional data can also increase the added value of data sharing, as can support logistic operators, freight terminals, and enforcement authorities in the use of digital data sharing. The availability of this data has a direct impact on their performance, enabling them to respond more effectively to unforeseen events and the current transport chain situation (European Commission, 2022). Real-time freight data (referred to as optional data) would help operators to react more quickly to delays, reduce dwell times, improve overall transport efficiency. All these facts will have a strong synergetic effect on the other indicators, which will also have a significant impact on the economic indicators. Sharing data will help to maximise collaboration between stakeholders, which can improve the quality of products and services provided (ICLEI, 2021).

Meeting the requirements listed above can ensure seamless and shared data, as well as the willingness of stakeholders to use a digital platform of data sharing.

4.5 Gap identification

By comparing stakeholders' needs and requirements with the current data exchange scenarios, it is possible to identify the gaps associated with the digitisation of freight transport. These gaps lead to a low use of digital information in freight transport and prevent the full introduction of digital data exchange in the transport market. The analysis of the gaps is linked to the previous chapters where the current state and the desired state (based on stakeholders' needs and requirements) were identified. By comparing the current state with the desired state, it is possible to define and describe the existing gaps that impede electronic data exchange (using digital platforms). These gaps are categorized into three main groups:

- digital gaps, which describe gaps from the perspective of digital data sharing,
- accessibility gaps, which describe gaps in terms of accessibility to data exchange systems and their utilization.
- legal gaps, which refer to gaps related to legislation.

4.5.1 Digitalisation gaps

- **Lack of safety and security measures:** the use of a single platform for data exchange may discourage logistic operators and freight terminals, as all documents should be shared via this platform. These documents contain important information about their customers, the routes they use, and other sensitive details. If their data is not protected at the highest level, they may refrain from using this platform due to concerns that their data could be misused or accessed by competitors, potentially resulting in a loss of business (e.g. competitors gaining a competitive advantage). As a result, individual stakeholders may opt to utilize multiple platforms with which they are already familiar and trust (Enache, 2023) (Coventry University, 2024).
- **Lack interoperability with existing systems:** logistic operators and freight terminals utilize different tools and methods to exchange required documents with the Enforcement authorities of the country in which they are established. In many cases, these authorities have the necessary data in digital form and can carry out the check without having to stop the vehicle (such as verifying driver's licenses, vehicle licence validity, etc.). However, in the case of international transport, authorities in another country may need to stop the transportation process to validate the vehicle, driver, goods, etc because they do not have this information and do not have access to the platforms of the country where the documents are available (Cefriel, 2023) (Coventry University, 2024) (T Bridge, 2024).
- **Lack of a technological standard:** stakeholders have diverse platforms that can be complex and time-consuming to integrate. Digital platforms used in transport are frequently developed using different standards and technology platforms, resulting in a lack of interoperability between them. Proper compatibility between these platforms is crucial to facilitate seamless communication and data exchange among all parties involved. It is essential to integrate the systems effectively to ensure that enforcement authorities have access to all the necessary data (Enache, 2023) (Cefriel, 2023) (T Bridge, 2024).
- **Tradition paper- based documents sharing:** many companies, especially SMEs, that are involved in transportation lack the infrastructure to use digital platform for data sharing. As a result, they prefer traditional paper-based communication methods over digital ones. Adopting new data-sharing practices may prove challenging for these companies, requiring the implementation of training and adaptation strategies to bridge this gap. However, this transition entails additional costs for them (Dasaklis, a iní, 2024) (Cefriel, 2023) (T Bridge, 2024) (Coventry University, 2024).

- **Low willingness of platforms providers:** several software providers are unwilling to share the required information to facilitate the integration of their software into a single platform. Without their consent, integration is not feasible, and failure to integrate would necessitate exchanging certain documents in paper form (Haapaniemi, 2022).
- **Lack of a real time single interface for mandatory data:** the existence of different platforms for exchanging various types of data makes the data exchange process between authorities within the same Member State and across different Member States more complex in terms of both time and expenses. The creation of a single real-time European interface for the exchange of transport data for instant checks is a common objective among the survey respondents. A single source of data exchange would facilitate the exchange of other non-mandatory data desired by stakeholders, as they are important sources of information that add value to transport process (Cefriel, 2023) (T Bridge, 2024).

4.5.2 Accessibility gaps

- **Non-acceptance of electronic documents:** as the analysis showed, paper-based forms of information and document exchange are still used in most of cases today. This factor represents an accessibility gap, mainly due to the low acceptance of electronic documents. For effective document and information exchange, this gap needs to be bridged so that information can be shared electronically by all stakeholders. Different data exchange requirements by enforcement authorities in different Member States (electronic data is accepted in one country and not in another) result in the need for paper documents on board the means of transport during international transport (Niestadt, 2020) (Cefriel, 2023) (Coventry University, 2024) (T Bridge, 2024).
- **High competition among stakeholders:** High competition, not only between different transport modes but also within stakeholder groups within the same transport mode (e.g. between road carriers – belong to logistic operators' group of stakeholders), may discourage individual stakeholders from adopting electronic data exchange. The questionnaire showed that not all stakeholders trust this method of data exchange (Lægran, Pitera, T, & Tørset, 2023) (Coventry University, 2024).
- **Additional costs for some stakeholders:** a digital platform can be costly to implement and maintain, and therefore, some stakeholders may have limited financial resources for implementation. Not all stakeholders currently use platforms for data exchange, in such cases, adopting these platforms may result in additional costs for these stakeholders (Ministry of Transport of the Slovak Republic, 2019), (T Bridge, 2024)
- **Language barrier:** within freight transport, there are several platforms used by different stakeholders across various Member States. The geo-political context represents a gap in terms of communication, as the platforms operate in different languages, creating difficulties in data exchange among stakeholders. Moreover, despite the potential for authorities to connect to stakeholder systems, they may struggle to understand the available data (CIVITTA, 2018).
- **Absence of e-documents:** The lack of electronic documents creates a significant gap in the international goods transportation. Authorities responsible for checking drivers, cargo, and the progress of the trip need to verify the accuracy of the documents. If these documents are not available electronically, the transport process may be halted for paper document verification. Currently, there is no obligation for using electronic documents, leading to their absence, and varying levels of acceptance of electronic documents among Member States and their authorities (only some Member States and their authorities accept online documents) (CIVITTA, 2018).

- **Driver's (un)readiness to use smart devices:** the logistic sector includes an aged workforce. The demography tends to have less exposure to and comfort with digital technologies. For some drivers, adopting new methods of data sharing could be challenging. For example, some freight terminals provide the drivers with instruction in paper form (where they have to park the trailer, which container the driver should take over, ...). If these data were to be exchanged digitally, it could present additional challenges, as older employees may require more time and resources to become familiar with new technologies (Dasaklis, a iní, 2024) (T Bridge, 2024).

4.5.3 Regulatory gaps

- **Lack of obligation to use digital platforms:** while the use of digital documents is permitted by legislation in some countries, it is not obligatory. However, these rules do not apply uniformly across all Member States, resulting in varying conditions regarding data exchange (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, 2018). The same eFTI Regulation 2020/1056 on electronic freight transport information, establishes a legal framework for electronic data exchange, which does not obligate, in a mandatory form, operators to electronically provide information to competent authorities.
- **Lack of harmonization of laws across the Member States:** individual Member States have their own laws, which leads to a lack of harmonization of laws and regulations and insufficient development of common standards (regulation, cooperation). Significant national differences exist in the acceptance and usage of digitalized documents and these differences create uncertainties for operators and businesses. Member States should cooperate and learn from each other to achieve the goals of digital data exchange between different stakeholders across different countries (DIGINNO, 2020). An international regulatory regime for freight transport, especially dangerous goods, appears necessary (Cefriel, 2023) (Coventry University, 2024) (T Bridge, 2024)
- **Lack of definition of responsibilities:** lack of clarity and ambiguity regarding who has the right to access which data and who is responsible for managing, protecting, and sharing it. Without clear guidelines and defined responsibilities, conflicts and confusion can arise between different transport actors regarding data access and use. For instance, if it is not specified which entity has the right to obtain certain data on loads, routes, or traffic conditions, unauthorized access, misuse of data, or breaches of confidentiality can occur. Furthermore, failure to define responsibilities can result in inefficient data management and governance in the transport sector. Unclear delineation of responsibilities for certain data and its management can lead to data duplication, inconsistency, or even data loss, resulting in increased costs, delays, and constraints in transport operations and management (Moschovou, Vlahogianni, & Rentziou, 2019).

5. Conclusions

The results obtained from T1.1 and T1.2 of Work Package1 have revealed the primary gaps that need to be addressed to the future digital logistics ecosystem. This deliverable has examined the main data exchange platforms utilized by key stakeholders in the logistic sector.

The initial section of the deliverable delves into the examination of the primary European platforms designed for data exchange among enforcement authorities, covering A2A interfaces, as well as B2B and B2A platforms. These platforms aim to streamline connectivity and communication among diverse stakeholders, comprising not only authorities but also logistic operators and freight terminals. The review of digital solutions highlights a connectivity disparity between the information stored within the platforms utilized by logistic operators and freight terminals and the data subject to control during authorities' inspections.

Several gaps emerge examining the current data exchange scenarios in freight transport and aligning it with stakeholders' needs and requirements. These gaps slow down the widespread adoption of digital information in freight transport and impede the realization of a fully digitalized data exchange ecosystem in the transportation sector.

These gaps can be broadly categorized into three main groups:

Firstly, digitalization gaps involve:

- The lack of robust safety and security measures, which discourage stakeholders from using single platforms for data exchange,
- Interoperability issues hinder the integration of diverse systems used by logistic operators and freight terminals, particularly in international contexts, together with absence of technological standards,
- Reliance on traditional paper-based document sharing persists among SMEs due to infrastructure limits and costs,
- Unwillingness of platforms providers to share the required information to facilitate the integration through data sharing systems.
- The absence of a real-time single interface for mandatory data exchange complicates processes, fostering inefficiencies and increasing operational costs.

Secondly, accessibility gaps include:

- Non-acceptance of electronic documents, high competition among stakeholders, and additional costs delay the widespread adoption of digital platforms.
- Language barriers and the absence of e-documents intensify challenges, particularly in international contexts.
- The reluctance of older workforce segments to adopt digital technologies further compounds accessibility issues.

Lastly, regulatory gaps lie in:

- The lack of obligatory use of digital platforms and the absence of harmonized laws across Member States.
- The lack of clarity and the ambiguity regarding data access rights and who is responsible for managing, protecting and sharing data.

Interoperability, standardization, regulatory harmonization, and stakeholder collaboration appear crucial to overcome the gaps and achieve a digital logistic ecosystem.

The digital ecosystem mission will be focused not only on facilitating the exchange of data between the different actors in the transport sector, but also opening the door to huge benefits for all stakeholders involved. Improved data exchange can significantly improve the conditions for transporting goods, speeding up processes, reducing costs and increasing the overall efficiency of the entire transport chain making road and rail transport really “European”.

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